

Supplementary Figure S3A: Preak Sdei enriched genera in healthy and diseased samples

Relative abundance were normalised by center-log ratio method. To detect enriched taxa, a wilcoxon test (alpha=0.05; Bonferroni correction) was conducted between disease and healthy (normal) samples.

Supplementary Figure S3A:

Preak Sdei enriched species in healthy and diseased samples

Supplementary Figure S3B: Rovieng enriched species in healthy and diseased samples

